

MODEL PREDICTING AND OPTIMIZATION FOR THE MARSHALL PROPERTIES OF COLD MIX-RECYCLED ASPHALT PAVEMENT (CRAP) USING RESPONSE SURFACE METHOD (RSM)

M. M. Musa^{*1}, T. S. Ijimdiya², A. Usman³ and I. Bello⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Civil Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

*marmusty111@gmail.com, mmmusa@abu.edu.ng

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ABSTRACT

Cold bitumen emulsion mixture (CBEM) is one of the most sustainable road construction material worldwide. When recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) is introduced in the mix, Cold-mix Recycled Asphalt Pavement (CRAP) is obtained, which is known for cost effectiveness and environmental friendliness because of its huge saving in cost of material and reduced green house gas emission (GHG). CRAP has been in use for different purposes in roads work. In this project cationic emulsion, cement, RAP, lime, aggregates were used as materials. Response surface method (RSM) was used for generating 6-nos predicting model equations for Marshall properties of CRAP and subsequently optimized solutions containing optimum factors and responses were obtained for the purpose of road wearing course layer. The results showed that bulk density, total void, and stability successfully fitted to quadratic model, VMA and VFA fitted to cubic model, while flow fitted to linear model, all with very high and satisfactory correlation factor R^2 (85% to 97%) with difference between predicted and adjusted value of not more than 0.2. Validation of the 6-predicting model equations were conducted using new set of laboratory samples casted with optimized solutions obtained from the RSM which showed that the difference between predicted and experimental values lied within the absolute discrepancy of 5%. This indicated that all the model equations could be used as predicting models for any CRAP material. It also showed that Samples that used 5% cements as filler satisfactorily performed with up to 50% of Rap in the wearing course.

Keywords: Cold-Mix, Recycled asphalt, Pavement, RSM

INTRODUCTION

The recent challenge posed by global warming and the need to reduce green house gas (GHG) emissions including CO_2 has led to a shift for many industries to reconsider many of their working practices and research. Cold mix technologies that are currently being promoted within the paving sector, leading to achieving degree of decarbonization of its operations (Orosa *et al.*, 2023). Cold mix asphalt (CMA) is being increasingly recognized as an important alternative world wide. One of the common types of CMA is cold bitumen emulsion mixture (CBEM) (Nassar *et al.*, 2016). When recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) is introduced in the mix Cold-mix recycled asphalt Pavement (CRAP) is obtained, which is known for cost effectiveness and environmental friendliness because of its huge saving in cost of material and reduced green house gas emission (GHG). CRAP has been in use for different purposes that includes sub base course layer and base course layer materials for roads. In this project emulsion, cement, RAP, lime, aggregates were used as materials to produce cold -mix recycled asphalt pavement for use in wearing course layer of the road. The advantages of using RAP in the cold mix asphalt includes reducing the exploration of virgin material,

saving cost, decreasing the use of natural resources, and providing less environmental damage (Filho *et al.*, 2020). Most of the studies reported in the literature on cold bitumen emulsions (CBEM) have focused on using the method adopted by the Asphalt Institute (Marshall Method for Emulsified Asphalt Aggregate Cold Mixture Design), with some modifications (Nassar *et al.*, 2016). The need to explore the use of a statistical tool like response surface method (RSM), to generate predicting model equations for marshall properties and optimize the mixture design of CBEM is the aim of this paper.

Response surface method (RSM) includes optimization procedures for the settings of factorial variables, such that the response reaches a desired maximum or minimum value. Response surface method (RSM) technique provides an in-depth understanding of the influence each mix design factor would have on the asphalt mixture performance. It is an effective alternative to optimize and understand the pavement mix design parameters effectively to produce optimal mixtures with less cost and sample runs (Usman *et al.*, 2021). The data-driven model equation was utilized to illustrate the different combinations of independent input factors that affect the outcome of a process or product. The

present study involved using result data of Marshall and volumetric properties of cold mix- recycled asphalt samples gotten from the laboratory test and importing into response surface method (RSM) statistical tool to generate predicting models of all the responses and optimize cold mix- recycled asphalt pavement (CRAP) factors. The investigative activities is limited to using Custom design method of response surface method.

Plate 1: Materials involved in the research

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The recycled asphalt Pavement (RAP) material, 30 years of age was sourced from Julius Berger construction site yard No-002 located along Kaduna-Zaria Road, its physical properties is presented in Table 2 and its gradation is shown in Table 4. Aggregates was sourced from Samaru quarry granite site, Zaria located opposite school of aviation, its physical properties are presented in Table 1 and its gradation is shown in Table 3. Cationic medium set emulsion was sourced from Katsina emulsion plant, Katsina state and its physical properties is presented in Table 6. Lime and OPC- 42.5N-cement were sourced from an open market. The chemical composition of lime is shown in Table 5.

Table-1 showed that the aggregates passed the required specifications as compared with the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) specification.

Table 2 show that the recycled asphalt pavement materials (RAP) passed the required specifications as compared with

Table 1: Physical properties of Aggregates

S/N	Test Done	Unit	ASTM Method	Results	Specifications	Remark
1	Aggregate crushing Value (CV)	%	ASTM C 535	23.7	< 30	OK
2	Aggregate Impact Value (IV)	%	ASTM D 5874	26.0	< 30	OK
3	Elongation Index (EI)	%	ASTM D 4791	17.32	< 20	OK
4	Flakiness Index (FI)	%	ASTM D 4791	21.14	< 25	OK
5	Specific gravity of Coarse aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.73	2.55-2.95	OK
6	Specific gravity of Fine aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.65	2.55-2.95	OK
7	Loss angeles Abrasion Value (LAAV)	%	ASTM C 535	23.4	< 40	OK
8	Water Absorption (ABS)	%	ASTM C 1585	0.54	2% Max	OK
9	Sand Equivalency/clay content	%	ASTM C 142	15.3	45% min	OK

Previous researchers like Yaro *et al.*, (2022), Usman *et al.*, (2021), Algraiti and Kavussi (2023), Al-Sabaei *et al.*, (2023), Flores *et al.*, (2020), Buchler *et al.*, (2018) and Filho *et al.*, (2020), all worked on similar area, on the asphalt pavement mixtures, though some have either used hot mix, super pave gyratory method of compaction, rejuvenator, worked on sub base layer of the road, or base layer of the road. But the difference of this research with their own is working on cold-mix recycled asphalt pavement for wearing course layer of the road, applying Marshall method of compaction, with the help of response surface method (RSM) and not using any type of rejuvenator.

the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) specification.

Table 3 show that the gradation of the fresh aggregates used in the mix passed the required specifications as compared with the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing (FMWH) specifications.

Table 4 showed that the gradation of the recycled asphalt pavement materials (RAP) used in the mix passed the required specifications as compared with the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing specifications (FMWH).

Table 2: Physical Properties of RAP

S/N	Test Done	Unit	ASTM Method	Results	Specifications	Remark
1	Aggregate crushing Value (CV)	%	ASTM C 535	22.5	< 30	OK
2	Aggregate Impact Value (IV)	%	ASTM D 5874	24.2	< 30	OK
3	Elongation Index (EI)	%	ASTM D 4791	12.13	< 20	OK
4	Flakiness Index (FI)	%	ASTM D 4791	17.00	< 25	OK
5	Specific gravity of Coarse aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.71	2.55-2.95	OK
6	Specific gravity of Fine aggregates	g/cm ³	ASTM C 127	2.62	2.55-2.95	OK
7	Water Absorption (ABS)	%	ASTM C 1585	0.34	2% Max	OK

Table 3: Gradation for the Job Mix (Fresh Aggregates)

S/N	Sieve Nos	Cumulative % passing(%)	FMWH Specification for Wearing Course	Remarks
1	12.5mm	99.64	85-100	Ok
2	9.5mm	77.80	75-92	Ok
3	6.4mm	80.60	65-82	Ok
4	2.8mm	63.20	50-65	Ok
5	1.25mm	50.80	36-51	Ok
6	600µm	37.90	26-40	Ok
7	300µm	23.60	18-30	Ok
8	150µm	20.50	13-24	Ok
9	75µm	7.30	7-14	Ok

Table 4: Gradation For the RAP Aggregates.

S/N	Sieve Nos	Cumulative % passing (%)	FMWH Specification for Binder Course	Remarks
1	12.5mm	78.3	55-80	Ok
2	9.5mm	69.3	47-70	Ok
3	6.4mm	58.6	40-60	Ok
4	2.8mm	41.4	27-45	Ok
5	1.25mm	28.3	20-34	Ok
6	600µm	18.5	14-27	Ok
7	300µm	10.5	8-20	Ok
8	150µm	5.5	5-15	Ok
9	75µm	1.9	2-7	Ok

Table 5 showed that the lime chemical composition has very high Calcium Oxide content (87.597 %) which is responsible for high value of stability when used in the mix.

Table 6 show that all the tests carried out on Cationic emulsion passed the required specifications as compared

with the European Standards (EN) and American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) specifications.

Table 6: Physical Properties of Cationic Emulsion

Property	Test results	Testing standards	Code
Color	Black to dark brown in a liquid state		
Particle charge	Positive	Positive	EN 1430
Viscosity at 25 °C (sec.)	118	30-150	EN 13614
Penetration, (dmms)	66	60-70	EN 1428
Bulk Density (g/cm ³)	1.014	0.97-1.02	ASTM D2726
Bitumen content	50%	40-80%	EN 1428

Table 5: Chemical Composition of Lime (Ca(OH)₂)

S/N	layer	Component	Type	concentration	Error	Units	Mole (%)	Error
1	1	SiO ₂	Calc	0.527	0.211	Wt.%	0.486	0.195
2	1	V ₂ O ₅	Calc	0.07	0.022	Wt.%	0.021	0.007
3	1	Cr ₂ O ₃	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
4	1	MnO	Calc	0.011	0.009	Wt.%	0.009	0.007
5	1	Fe ₂ O ₃	Calc	0.188	0.017	Wt.%	0.065	0.006
6	1	Co ₃ O ₄	Calc	0.072	0.01	Wt.%	0.016	0.002
7	1	NiO	Calc	0.02	0.005	Wt.%	0.015	0.004
8	1	CuO	Calc	0.063	0.009	Wt.%	0.044	0.006
9	1	Nb ₂ O ₃	Calc	0.103	0.352	Wt.%	0.025	0.083
10	1	MoO ₃	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
11	1	WO ₃	Calc	0.069	0.043	Wt.%	0.016	0.01
12	1	P ₂ O ₅	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
13	1	SO ₃	Calc	0.207	0.068	Wt.%	0.143	0.047
14	1	CaO	Calc	87.597	0.483	Wt.%	86.546	0.477
15	1	MgO	Calc	7.526	6.705	Wt.%	10.346	9.218
16	1	K ₂ O	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
17	1	BaO	Calc	0.073	0.067	Wt.%	0.026	0.024
18	1	Al ₂ O ₃	Calc	2.35	1.081	Wt.%	1.277	0.588
19	1	Ta ₂ O ₅	Calc	0.065	0.036	Wt.%	0.008	0.005
20	1	TiO ₂	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
21	1	ZnO	Calc	0.018	0.008	Wt.%	0.012	0.005
22	1	Ag ₂ O	Calc	0	0	Wt.%	0	0
23	1	Cl	Calc	0.462	0.036	Wt.%	0.722	0.056
24	1	ZrO ₂	Calc	0.104	0.092	Wt.%	0.047	0.041
25	1	SnO ₂	Calc	0.474	1.175	Wt.%	0.174	0.432

Plate 2: (a) Prepared test samples and (b) Automated compaction machine

Table 7: ANOVA of Responses by RSM

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F-value	P-value	Observation
a-Bulk unit weight (BUW)						
Model	0.1604	10	0.0160	55.22	< 0.0001	significant
Residual	0.0229	79	0.0003			
Cor Total	0.1833	89				
Model type	Quadratic					
b-Total void in the mix (AV)-%						
Model	448.85	10	44.89	87.60	< 0.0001	significant
Residual	40.48	79	0.5124			
Cor Total	489.33	89				
Model type	Quadratic					
c-Void in mineral Aggregate (%)						
Model	489.41	13	37.65	128.82	< 0.0001	significant
Residual	22.21	76	0.2922			
Cor Total	511.62	89				
Model type	Cubic					
d-Void filled by bitumen (%)						
Model	8313.01	14	593.79	202.65	< 0.0001	significant
Residual	219.76	75	2.93			
Cor Total	8532.77	89				
Model type	Cubic					
e-Stability (KN)						
Model	1777.84	8	222.23	59.36	< 0.0001	significant
Residual	303.26	81	3.74			
Cor Total	2081.10	89				
Model type	Quadratic					
f-Flow (mm)						
Model	21.71	5	4.34	103.01	< 0.0001	significant
Residual	3.54	84	0.0421			
Cor Total	25.25	89				
Model type	Linear					

df: degree of freedom, F-values: Fisher-statistical test values, p-values: probability values.

Methods

Laboratory sampling preparation and mix design

Marshall's design mix approach was used as stated in ASTM D6927 to evaluate compacted specimen samples for the design method. In the Marshall mix design, variables such as environment and traffic loading were considered when evaluating the basic engineering properties of asphalt mixtures. The sample specimens were prepared using standard method of mixing, and compaction. The asphalt mixtures were compacted with 75 blows back and front using the Marshall automated compactor machine. After the compaction, the samples' average diameter and thickness were approximately 100mm and 70 mm, respectively. Samples were adequately positioned on a leveled and smooth surface at ambient temperature before subsequent testing to determine the optimum bitumen content (OBC) and other mechanical performance tests.

A total of 105-number samples were prepared using Marshall method containing different combinations and with three specimens for each, the average value was observed and recorded for each, Marshall and volumetric analysis were carried out and their respective bulk densities, total voids in the mix (AV), total voids in mineral aggregates (VMA), Voids filled by bitumen (VFB), stability (s), and flow (f) where established. The asphalt samples were placed in a water bath for 40 minutes at 60 °C before testing for stability and flow.

Research methodology

See (Figure 1)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RSM-Statistical analysis and modelling:

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and regression analysis for each of the responses were carried out and 3D response plot contours were generated from the RSM to demonstrate the interaction between factors and responses and to explain the influence of input variables on the output response. For each model, the factors were drawn on the X and Y-axes, while the response was drawn on the Z-axis. Figures 2(a and b) to 7 (a and b) shows the 3D response plot contour of the model and it was observed to have a great synergetic

effect between the input variables. The contour plot's color indicates response values, with blue to green to yellow to red indicating a lower to medium to higher to a more optimized interaction region. Table 7 shows that the ANOVA results of all the 6- responses have Models- P-values of less than 0.0500 which signifies that all the models are significant.

Table 8 shows that the regression analysis results of all the 6- responses have very high and satisfactory correlation factors R² (85 % to 97 %) with difference between predicted and adjusted value of not more than 0.2 which translates to efficiency of all the models.

Legend for model equations

A =Emulsion, B= Cement, C= Dust, D= Lime, E=RAP

Bulk Density

The regression model equation is given by equation-i

$$\text{Bulk Density} = 2.18 - 0.0283A + 0.0025B - 0.014C - 0.0013D - 0.0454E - 0.0098AD + 0.0113CD - 0.0336A^2 + 0.0092D^2 + 0.0298E^2 \quad (i)$$

It is observed from figure2a that as the cement increases the bulk density increases, this is because the voids in the mix were being filled by the cement. while figure 2b shows that as the percentage of lime increases, the density barely changes, this is because the percentage of lime being added was too small to affect the density.

Total Void (AV):

The regression model equation is given by equation-ii.

$$AV = 12.25 - 2.76A - 0.3226B + 0.4488C - 0.0191D + 1.84E + 0.43AD - 0.835BD - 1.11CD + 1.02A^2 - 1.16E^2 \quad (ii)$$

It is observed that from figure 3a as the percentage of lime increases, the total voids gradually decreases, this is because the lime particles were filling the existing voids between the mix particles pores.

While from Figure 3b it is seen that as the percentage of emulsion content increases the total voids in the mix reduces while as the % of RAP increases, the total voids increase. This is because the emulsion particles were filling the voids in the mix while there was lot of voids content in

Table 8: Regression Analysis Values for the Responses

Statistical analysis	BUW	AV (%)	VMA (%)	VFB (%)	S(KN)	F(mm)
Standard dev.	0.0170	0.7158	0.5406	1.71	1.93	0.2053
Mean	2.13	10.33	27.12	61.50	10.13	3.40
Coefficient of variance	0.7989	6.93	1.99	2.78	19.10	6.04
R ²	0.8748	0.9173	0.9566	0.9742	0.8543	0.8598
Adjusted R ²	0.8590	0.9068	0.9492	0.9694	0.8399	0.8514
Predicted R ²	0.8306	0.8816	0.9324	0.9590	0.8298	0.8428
Adeq Precision	24.8893	35.8848	41.2845	57.7070	28.7467	41.1845

Correlation coefficient (R)

Figure 1: Overall Research Methodology

the RAP already because of the pores between the aggregate particles.

Total Void in Mineral Aggregates (VMA)

The regression model equation is given by equation-iii.

$$VMA = 27.82 + 3.36A - 0.5031B + 0.0934C - 2.29D + 0.5158E + 0.3215AD - 3.01BD - 3.34CD + 0.8319A^2 + 0.2909B^2 - 0.7759E^2 + 2.38B^2D + 1.2E^3 \quad (iii)$$

From Figure 4a it is observed that as the percentage of cement and lime increase the VMA decreases, this is because the voids in the mix were being filled by the cement and lime particles. Similarly, from figure 4b it is observed that as the percentage of dust increases, the VMA

Figure 2a: 3D Plot of Bulk Density vs Cement and Emulsion, while Figure 2b: 3D Plot of Bulk Density vs Lime and Emulsion

Figure 3a: 3D Plot of Total Void (AV) vs Lime and Cement, while Figure 3b: 3D Plot of Total Void vs Emulsion Content and RAP

Fig-11 3D surface plot for VMA Vs Lime and Dust

Figure 4a: 3D Plot of VMA vs Cement and Lime Content, while Figure 4b: 3D Plot of VMA vs Lime and Dust

decreases, this is because the voids in the mix were being filled by the dust filler also.

Total Void Filled by Bitumen (VFB)

The regression model equation is given by equation-iv.

$$VFB = 54.77 + 15.2 A + 1.13B - 0.7251C + 7.64D - 1.44E - 1.24AD + 10.46BD + 11.42CD - 4.97A^2 - 0.3844B^2 - 7.89B^2D - 3.46E^3 \tag{iv}$$

It is observed from figure 5a that as the emulsion content increases the VFB increases, this is because more voids content in the mix were being replaced by bitumen. While from figure 5b it is observed that as the percentage of RAP

increases, the VFB reduces, this is because of the voids content in the RAP already in existence.

Stability

The regression model equation is given by equation-v

$$Stability = 5.78 - 1.88A + 3.49B - 0.6381C + 0.6035D - 1.97E - 1.08AB - 2.35A^2 + 5.75E^2 \tag{v}$$

It is observed from figure-6a that as the cement increases the stability increases while as the emulsion content increases the stability increases until optimum value is reached before it starts decreasing, this is because of the high content of calcium oxide in cement, while the emulsion particles keep filling-in the void in the mix until

Figure 5a: 3D Plot of VFB vs Cement and Emulsion Content, Figure-5b:3D Plot of VFB vs RAP Content and Emulsion

Figure 6a: 3D Plot of Stability vs Cement and Emulsion Content, while Figure 6b: 3D Plot of Stability vs RAP and Emulsion Content

Figure 7a: 3D Plot of Flow vs Cement and Emulsion Content, Figure 7b: 3D plot of Flow vs RAP Content and Dust.

Figure 8a and b: Plot of Predicted vs Actual Values for Bulk Density and Total Void (AV) respectively

Figure 8c and d: Plot of Predicted vs Actual Values for VMA and VFB respectively

Figure 8e and f: Plot of Predicted vs Actual Values for Stability and Flow respectively

it fills all the voids and then get saturated with emulsion. While from figure 6b it is observed that as the percentage of RAP increases, the Stability decreases then later it starts increasing, this shows that there is presence of the voids content in the RAP that causes the abnormal behavior in the stability of the mix.

Flow

The regression model equation is given by equation-vi.

$$\text{Flow} = 2.49 + 0.4867A - 0.8463B - 0.4117C + 0.1702D + 0.2344E \quad (vi)$$

It is observed from figure 7a that as the cement content increases the flow decreases while as the emulsion content increases the flow increases, this is because of the calcium oxide present in the cement that causes rigidity and by doing that reduces the flow while the presence of fluid content with carbon dioxide in the emulsion makes the mix more flexible with flow tendency.

From Figure 7b it is observed that as the percentage of RAP increases, the Flow increases, this is because of the residual bitumen content of the RAP that may be in reaction with the mix. The trends of the RSM 3D- plots con-tours obtained for the responses including bulk density, total void in the mix (AV), stability and flow are similar to the following research works: Yaro *et al.*, (2022), Saeed *et al.*, (2021), and Nasar *et al.*, (2016).

From all the figures above (8a, b, c, d, e &f) it is clear that the predicted consistency is largely consistent with the actual results obtained by the experimental tests, almost all of the points of replies are scattered close to the equality line. This illustrates how accurate the developed models are.

Optimization

Table 9 shows optimized solution containing optimum factors, indicating that the mix can satisfactorily work with 50% RAP content.

From Table 9, optimized solution was generated using constraints and goals which also passes all the required specifications. The optimized solution by the RSM proposed factors of 7.28 % of emulsion content, 5 % cement filler, 2 % dust filler, 0.139 lime, 50 % RAP content, to achieve the responses of 2.077 g/cm³ bulk density, total voids of 10 %, 25.56 % VMA, 60.69 % VFB, 5.16 KN stability, and 2.72mm flow. The combined desirability of this selected solution is 72 % which is quite commendable.

Validation of prediction models

Table 10 shows Model equations validation results, it is observed that the absolute percentage of discrepancies between the experimental and predicted values of the responses were all observed to be minimal, within the allowable range of < 5 % which is an indication that the model equations are efficient and can be used for prediction in cold mix asphalt.

A validation test was conducted to reverify and validate the predictive model equations. To assess the performance of the model equations, new series of laboratory tests with three specimens for each were prepared. the average value was observed and recorded. The absolute percent discrepancy between the experimental and predicted values

of the responses was observed to be minimal, within the allowable range of < 5% as reflected in Table 10.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The following conclusions are found from this research:

1. The results showed that Bulk Density, Total Void (AV), and Stability responses successfully fitted to quadratic model equations, VMA and VFA fitted to cubic model equations, while flow fitted to linear model equations, with very high and satisfactory correlation factor R² (85 % to 97 %) with difference between predicted and adjusted value of not more than 0.2.
2. Samples that used 5 % cements as filler can perform satisfactorily with up to 50 % of RAP in the wearing course.
3. From the optimization and prediction, RSM proved to be useful statistical tool, and the model equations proved to be efficient through validation.

Recommendations

Based on the result obtained in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Bulk density, Total Void (AV) and Stability should be fitted to quadratic model equation, VMA and VFA should be fitted to cubic model equation, while flow should be fitted to linear model equation.
2. The prediction models generated can be used for cold mix asphalt projects.
3. Minimum of 5 % cement as filler should be used for production of cold mix wearing course asphalt using 50 % RAP content.
4. 7.28 % emulsion content should be adopted as optimized value for any cold mix wearing course asphalt containing RAP of up to 50 %.

Table 9: Optimized solution with the level of desirability

N	Emu	Cem	Dust	Lime	RAP	B.Density	AV (10-14%)	VMA	VFB	S (>3.5KN)	F (2-4mm)	Des.
1	7.280	5.000	2.000	0.139	50.000	2.077	10.000	25.558	60.694	5.161	2.720	0.724

Table 10: Average validation results of the prediction models

N	Value Type	B. density	AV	VMA	VFB	S	F
1	Experimental value	2.005	12.53	27.62	54.62	5.64	2.65
2	Predicted Value	1.95	12.68	28.25	55.33	5.79	2.59
3	Absolute Discrepancy (%)	2.7	1.2	2.3	1.3	2.7	2.3

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